

EARLY DIAGNOSIS AND DEVELOPMENT OF METHODS AND MEANS OF PREVENTING TRACE ELEMENT DISEASES IN COWS, AS WELL AS DYSPEPSIA IN CALVES OF NEONATAL ETIOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6748738>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

is to study the etiology, early diagnosis and development of methods and means of prevention of trace element diseases in cows, as well as dyspepsia in neonatal calves.

ABSTRACT

The state of animal health and productivity as a whole depend on metabolic processes, the intensity of which is largely regulated by the provision of the body with microelements, vitamins and other metabolic products.

Materials and methods of research

The researches have been carried out on farms of Bukhara, Navoi and Samarkand regions. The diets of dry cows were investigated for content of peridigestible protein, carbohydrates, carotene, calcium, phosphorus, fibre, as well as copper, cobalt, manganese and zinc.

In each series there were three groups of dry cows of red-steppe breed, 5-7 cows in each, selected according to the principle of analogy. Cows from the first group were fed the preparation LPP-1 (80 g bentonite, 100 mg copper sulphate, 100 mg potassium iodide, 80 mg manganese sulphate, 20 mg cobalt chloride, 200 000 IU of vitamin A, 100 000 IU of vitamin D3, 100 000 IU of vitamin D3, 100 000 IU of vitamin E). IU

vitamin D3, vitamin E 80 mg), the second group received premix LPP-2 (100 g bentonite, 200 mg copper sulphate, 150 mg potassium iodide, 100 mg manganese sulphate, 40 mg cobalt chloride, 250 000 IU vitamin A, 150 000 IU vitamin D3, vitamin E 100 mg). The third group of animals was kept on the diet adopted by the farm. The preparation was administered to the experimental animals daily during the whole dry period. Blood was drawn from the experimental cows at the beginning of the experiments and every 20 days until the end of the experiments and examined for erythrocytes, haemoglobin, glucose, total protein and reserve alkalinity by conventional methods, as well as for amounts of some trace elements (Si, Co,

Mn, Zn, I) by atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

Results of the research and discussion

In diets of dry cows a deficiency of carbohydrates, carotene, phosphorus, copper, cobalt, manganese, zinc and an excess of peridigestible protein, calcium and fibre was revealed. The content of sugar in the ration was 47.3%, phosphorus 86.1%, copper 61.0, cobalt 77.4, manganese 69.3 and zinc 65.8%.

Studies have established that the preparations used by us, especially as part of LPP-2, lead to normalisation of all types of metabolism in pregnant cows, as evidenced by blood values.

Newborn calves from the experimental group cows had a higher level of physiological maturity and resistance. Their body weight was 8.9-11.0% higher

than that of the control group cows. The incidence of dyspepsia among newborn calves decreased significantly in the experimental groups. At the same time, the disease, as a rule, was characterised by a mild course and ended with recovery. In the control group, dyspepsia was observed in three newborn calves (30%) and one was fatal.

Thus, the use of LPP-2 as a group prophylactic therapy normalizes the disorders of mineral and vitamin metabolism in the maternal body and increases the quality of colostrum. All this has a positive effect on the clinical and biochemical status of newborn calves, their resistance, and ultimately reduces the occurrence and development of dyspepsia of neonatal etiology.

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